

IMPROVING THE WORKFORCE QUALITY THROUGH THE PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION MODERNIZATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7495140>

Abstract

The article examines the goals, tasks and measures for the further modernization of the professional education' organization and content as a guarantee for fulfilling its immanent functions of Ukraine' socio-economic development in the conditions of globalization competitive challenges. The professional education' accessibility and quality play an important role in overcoming the challenges and risks of globalization and integration in the circle of partners and competitors, both among countries with a developed market economy operating on the modern technological basis, and among developing countries claiming for increase of budget revenues from traditional specialization branches, as well as for diversification and knowledge-intensive modernization of national economies. Civilization trends and economic practices of developed countries, powerful cross-border associations and transnational corporations, aspirations for cultural, foreign economic, socio-political integration into the EU structures, as well as measures for their implementation, are spreading in modern Ukraine. Such trends stimulate national civil society to actualize a number of requests to provide an average individual' decent opportunities to meet the needs for quality education services, profession acquirement, confirmation and increase of qualification regardless of the residence place, equalization of the appropriate starting conditions in local communities and regions, as well as to improve the efficiency of public and state control over the corresponding legislative and social-labor guarantees' implementation.

Keywords: professional education, labor potential, workforce, innovations, socio-economic policy, Ukraine' prospects.

Introduction. Modernization of socium approaches to the organization of professional education (higher and vocational), its institutional foundations, principles, methodology of functioning at the national, regional and local levels is an important condition for improving the efficiency and results of the national economy, the spectrum of structures and mechanisms for its innovation and personnel provision, implementation of the population' basic constitutional rights regarding professional self-realization, comprehensive development and education throughout life, obtaining decent labour income, improving the level and quality of life of an average person by one's own efforts. These tasks' solution is the necessary prerequisite for the effective response of the state, its economic system and the whole society to the challenges of world-integration and globalization processes, first of all, regarding the competitiveness of both producers and workers, as well as the technological support of the business processes' set in the economy and non-economic life spheres.

Brief Literature Review. Modern studies pay considerable attention to the substantiation of: accents and priorities for improving the functioning mechanisms, structure, content of professional education in its links' spectrum; interrelationships of this public institution with other socium macrostructures (in particular, while determining the level, quality and rates of socio-economic development); the system of professional education' impacts on the parameters of innovative processes and competitive rivalries in the spheres of their deployment in the globalized world, as well as among a number of integrated cross-border business, foreign economic, cultural and educational structures [1–16].

In particular, some researchers are identifying

risks and opportunities, developing approaches to the higher and vocational education quality' improvement, taking into account the requirements of world-wide globalization and integration processes for professional training, the economically active population' qualifications, the workforce' competitiveness [1–5]. At the same time, the problems, inherent to the various stages of the latest period of the professional education system' functioning, are identified and analyzed through the needs of increasing of the higher and vocational institutions' economic efficiency, balancing regional labor markets, implementing a number of socio-economic reforms [6–10]. An important direction of studies is the provision of the professional education' proper role in stimulating, spreading, capitalizing the scientific and technological progress' achievements, carrying out a systemic innovative influence on business and society [1–3; 11; 12]. Also it is appropriate to note the works on the assessment of the current situation and prospects for ensuring the stable functioning of the vocational and technical education sector that is extremely important for providing qualified workers for territorial economic systems and social protection of the population' vulnerable strata [8; 13–16].

The purpose of the article is to determine the goals, tasks and measures for the further modernization of the professional education' organization and content as a guarantee for fulfilling its immanent functions of Ukraine' socio-economic development in the conditions of globalization competitive challenges.

Main results. The competitiveness of persons acquiring professional education, so as workers and specialists of various qualifications on the labor market di-

rectly depends on the modernity level of the comprehensive and professional training that they have received, which is ensured by the consistent updating of the content, methodology, technological base, methods of teaching professional knowledge, relevant academic disciplines, their materials, programs, practices, etc., as well as of the qualifications' and competencies' level of the scientific and pedagogical staff in the spectrum of professional education institutions (the establishments for career guidance, vocational diagnosis, vocational training, advanced training, career development). At the same time, educational cycles' and programs' saturation with the latest knowledge, means of their teaching and assimilation is not a sufficient condition for increasing the competitiveness of pupils, students and graduates; it should be supplemented by strengthening the focus on the relevant knowledge' practical application, assimilation of appropriate abilities, skills, competencies within the framework of seminars, laboratory classes, practice in production, etc.

An important task of the professional education' modernization is the consistent activity of the Ministry of Education and Science, supported by other executive and legislative power bodies, the broad scientific community and interested public institutions, regarding the consistent updating the scientific and worldview content of the set of theoretical and practical disciplines of the professional education links' spectrum, as well as improving their personnel, scientific and pedagogical, technical and technological support. A significant criterion for the relevant measures' competence is the constant communication of professional education institutions, this sphere' state management with employers' representatives, who are able to the quickest and effective assessment of the prospects and production value of the scientific and technical progress' achievements, relevant professional knowledge, abilities, skills of searchers in the labor market.

An additional factor in the requirements' growth for the professional education balancing and quality rising are the Ukraine' post-war revival demands, which would lead to an increase in the need for qualified personnel, primarily for workers with integrated technological specialties, the shortage of whom in certain sectors and territorial economic systems was acutely felt and consistently grew even in the pre-war period. At the same time, we should note further actualization of the problems of the professional training' and mobility' quality of specialists with higher education, caused by the dynamic change of social approaches to their qualifications' recognition and value assessment, the growth of requirements for consistent professional self-development throughout the working life as essential conditions for the competitiveness reproducing of an economically active person on the labor market.

The main goals of the Ukrainian professional education system' modernization should be grouped according to the direction areas on: spreading and affirming the standards and requests for quality education throughout life in society and business practices; improving the spatial organization of the higher and vocational institutions' network with a focus on increasing

the crisis resilience parameters of both the territorial educational subsystems and their elements, as well as the totality of life spheres in the regions and the whole state. Both grouping directions of the professional education modernization' main goals are combined through a series of goals embodying the next direction – on rising the innovative potential of communities and the economy, broadcasting and increasing the creativity mechanisms' effectiveness as a source and incentives for competitive socio-economic development, business diversification.

Thus, the goals for dissemination and affirmation of standards and requests for quality education throughout life in society and business practices include:

- ensuring the scientific capacity and practical orientation of professional education at all stages of its organization and in the range of institutions that provide career guidance, vocational diagnosis, vocational, advanced training and professional development for various categories of the population throughout life, in accordance with modern achievements of world science and economics, in particular, in the field of production technologies, management, public informing and enlightenment, worldview formation;

- balancing the state standards of professional education and the criteria for the functioning of non-state, including informal, systems and institutions for its provision and recognition, certification of job seekers on the labor market and hired workers at enterprises of various ownership forms;

- further increasing the autonomy of professional education institutions (higher, vocational) in determining their own specialization, the content and teaching technologies of the general and proper vocational training' optional component, the funding sources' structure, bases for the pupils' and students' production practices, management and marketing strategies on the educational services' market and in the spheres of public relations, cooperation with employers;

- rising up the availability of professional education, retraining, advanced training and development throughout the life for the population' vulnerable groups and categories at the expense of educational vouchers, state and non-profit institutions' loans, as well as through the personnel training' targeted order for depressed areas and settlement systems;

- stimulating the consistent growth of the Ukrainian population' solvent demand for the professional education', retraining', advanced training' services within the framework of a long-term strategy for raising the life' level and quality of the economically active population, equalizing the initial conditions of the younger generation' living.

In turn, the goals for improving the higher and vocational institutions network' spatial organization with a focus on increasing the crisis resilience parameters of educational subsystems and the totality of life spheres involve:

- intensifying the formation processes of regional scientific, educational and industrial clusters integrated into territorial, including cross-border, busi-

ness systems (in particular, the spectrum of free economic zones) and their innovative infrastructure;

- optimizing the cycle of vocational and career guidance, professional education and training of various specializations' personnel for national territorial economic systems, coordinated in the structure of professional education branches (higher, vocational, state, communal and non-state institutions of professional development and employment promotion);

- increasing the socio-economic efficiency of vocational education institutions in conditions of funding shortages, which threatens their viability in spite of the national economy' growing needs for qualified workers;

- equalizing a socially and economically active life' initial conditions, regardless of the individual's origin, psychophysiological characteristics, and residence' place;

- balancing the regulatory support and mechanisms for the formation and financing of the state and regional segments of the personnel training order in accordance with the long-term strategy of the Ukrainian economy' specialization and diversification.

Among the important tasks, the solution of which will contribute to the above-mentioned goals' achievement, in particular regarding the improvement of the educational process' structure, material support and content, the following should be highlighted:

- improving the standards and programs of professional education, teachers' training programs, promoting the diversification of the personnel training', professional development' and retraining' system in the context of the urgent and strategic needs for increasing the goods' and services' national production, balancing its specialization and territorial organization (primarily, in accordance with the current situation and prospects of the production and technological base' modernization, the realities and orientations of the national manufacturers' positioning on internal and foreign sales' markets);

- further large-scale implementing of information and communication technologies, corresponded with EU standards and best examples of other worldwide developed countries (including such technologies in the field of: distance learning; development of electronic software for education, knowledge' and skills' quality testing, textbooks and methodological literature), in the professional education institutions of various ownership forms;

- increasing the level of educational, methodological and financial autonomy of higher and vocational education institutions, simplifying their procedures for revenues' using from profile activities (including ones from paid educational services) for the needs of the educational process' modernizing, arranging the pupils' and students' living conditions;

- activating constructive dialogue of three-party institutions (i. e., mechanism for regulation of labor and kindred economic and political relations based on equal interaction and cooperation of the employees', employers', state' representatives) and public-private partnership regarding the implementation of workers' and specialists' integrated specialties standards, non-

formal education' recognition, qualifications' acquisition and confirmation in non-state institutions and within the framework of on-the-job training.

A significant progress in achieving the goals of strengthening the professional education' practical orientation, implementing its innovative functions, producing modern competitive abilities and skills of pupils, students, graduates, developing the workforce' creative potential will stimulate the solution of tasks, such as:

- restoring the large-scale practice of on-the-job professional training as an effective tool for: improving the employees' qualifications and remuneration level; modernizing professional education' standards and programs in accordance with the employers' requests; diversifying funding sources of professional education institutions (higher, vocational); forming industrial and innovative territorial clusters of various specializations with the active participation of universities and vocational schools;

- encouraging employers to fund personnel professional education, retraining and advanced training by optimizing the taxation practice of economic entities that carry out and increase such expenses;

- further progressing of the system of continuous professional education throughout life, including on the basis of the appropriate services' provision at employment centers (in the form of courses for registered unemployed and additional employment' seekers), as well as at state and non-state social protection structures that take care for pensioners, disabled people, the population' marginal categories;

- substantiating, providing effective financing mechanisms for the state and regional personnel training orders to meet the Ukrainian economy' urgent needs, in particular, the staffing needs for the territories' post-war development through: the restoration of the living environment' safety and acceptable quality (mine clearance, development of critical infrastructure – facilities and networks of electricity and heat generation, water supply, transport communications of freight and passenger transit, their logistics, etc.); revitalization of the country's specialization branches and export-oriented industries that have been preserved (from mining to instrument and machine building, from agro-processing to recreational); specialists' and support staff' provision for regional systems of health care, social protection, education, local construction and food enterprises;

- optimizing mechanisms for recognizing national documents on obtaining professional education (diplomas, attestations, certificates) in EU countries.

A significant role in fulfilling the needs of modernized national and territorial economic complexes and labor markets for qualified personnel (workers, specialists) is played by measures for implementing the Strategy of the vocational (vocational and technical) education development until 2023, approved by the collegium of the Ministry of education and science in 2020. The measures carried out in recent years within the framework of above-mentioned Strategy are primarily aimed at the:

- consolidation of vocational education institutions' management at local level, their transfer to communal ownership, plans' presentation for the developing regional networks of such institutions, including through their consolidation;

- modernization of the professional education infrastructure through the educational and practical centers' establishment – i.e., these are institutions with new equipment and technique that provide services for students to acquire practical skills, improve qualifications or retrain adults with the funds of the state budget, local budgets, professional education institutions' special funds, as well as with the business companies' support;

- professional education standards' establishment and improvement, educational programs' updating, improvement of teachers' qualifications in active cooperation with employers' institutions within the framework of implementation of the National qualifications' system subordinated to state professional standards.

Improving the training of Ukrainian universities' and vocational schools' pupils and students for professional activities should be carried out by:

- implementing the vocational institutions' rights to independent educational programs' composition taking into account the results of territorial labor markets' studies, the interdisciplinary principle, as well as to this programs' supplementation with a segment formed from disciplines chosen by the students themselves;

- stimulating connections between vocational education institutions and employers to conduct students' industrial practice, to acquire their necessary professional skills and initial qualification level;

- fulfilling applied scientific research programs in higher educational institutions; obtaining by these institutions the status of resource educational, methodical and research centers for priority economy sectors of the regions and the whole country; stimulation of vocational institutions to participate in the activities of such centers, territorial educational, scientific and production complexes, as well as in activities of a range of innovative structures (industrial parks, technological parks, scientific and research consortia, innovative and technological clusters, etc.);

- establishing administrative and fiscal measures that ensure: first jobs for graduates, their early adaptation in primary workplace positions; the encouragement of enterprises and organizations that provide practice bases and first jobs for graduates, conclude contracts with educational institutions for the goods' and services' production (including services for personnel professional development and retraining), as well as for scientific research.

Conclusions. The professional education' accessibility and quality play an important role in overcoming the challenges and risks of globalization and integration in the circle of partners and competitors, both among countries with a developed market economy operating on the modern technological basis, and among developing countries claiming for increase of budget revenues from traditional specialization branches, as

well as for diversification and knowledge-intensive modernization of national economies.

On the other hand, civilization trends and economic practices of developed countries, powerful cross-border associations and transnational corporations, aspirations for cultural, foreign economic, socio-political integration into the EU structures, as well as measures for their implementation, are spreading in modern Ukraine. Such trends stimulate national civil society to actualize a number of requests to provide an average individual' decent opportunities to meet the needs for quality education services, profession acquirement, confirmation and increase of qualification regardless of the residence place, equalization of the appropriate starting conditions in local communities and regions, as well as to improve the efficiency of public and state control over the corresponding legislative and social-labor guarantees' implementation.

In this context, the main directions for the modernization of the professional education throughout a life combine:

- its popularization and establishment of the management and financing effective system through the public-private partnership and improvement of the professional education' content and quality;

- further consolidation of the efforts of the tripartite public dialogue' participants regarding the professional education development in the direction of solving both corporate and local tasks for providing qualified specialists and workers, so as for the modernizing territorial economic complexes and labor markets;

- development and improvement of professional education standards for a number of professions, educational programs' update, rise of teachers' qualifications, in particular, due to the active cooperation with employers' institutions during the further implementation of the National Qualifications System, subordinated to state professional standards;

- strengthening the autonomy of the professional education institutions' spectrum (higher, vocational ones), as well as the local authority' management of vocational and technical schools;

- further planning of the vocational education institutions' regional networks, including through their consolidation;

- modernizing the professional education infrastructure due to the creation of educational and practical centers with high-grade equipment and technique that provide services for obtaining practical skills by students, improving qualifications or retraining adults with the funds of the state and local budgets, professional education institutions' special funds, as well as with the business companies' support.

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